

**THE CURRENT STATE OF THE INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN
ENERGY MANAGEMENT SCIENCE TEACHING IN TECHNICAL
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS**

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Abstract: In this article, raising the quality of education to a new level is based on the role of modern approaches in the development of basic competences of students in the field of science. The importance of an integrative approach in the development of basic competencies is highlighted.

Keywords: Competence, integration, communication, technology, e-learning, knowledge, skill, competence, ability, efficiency, flexibility, achievement, success, comprehension, "effectiveness, learnability, kocca, characteristic, quality, quantity.

The issue of education is a process that regularly adapts to the requirements of the times and improves in harmony with scientific and technical achievements. One of the unique aspects of the educational system of the 21st century is the demand for students to be able to apply the knowledge they have acquired in higher technical educational institutions in life, the improvement of the State educational standards and programs, in other words, the integration of the integrative approach into the content of the educational system, the formation of the concept of achieving its educational results.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, "If we look at history, we see that technical sciences were the fundamental basis for the creation of almost all discoveries and technologies in the world. "Indeed, it is impossible to achieve results in today's

demanding areas such as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, IT, water and energy-saving technologies, without a deep understanding of the principles of Energy Management."

Based on the analysis of materials on the integrative approach in education, the following information can be given.

The words "Competence" and "Competence" began to enter the scientific literature for the first time. For example, the American linguist N. Chomsky's "Aspects of the Theory of Syntax" of the term competence in relation to the theory of linguistics defines the fundamental difference between "competence (knows, speaks, hears) and consumes (actually uses the language in specific cases)" or "the ability of a person to perform some activity" ability" can be quoted.

B.S. Abdullaeva in her scientific research work showed definitions for improving the integration of Mathematics with other subjects.

G.A. Asilova summarizing the definitions of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" in her thesis, "competence" is the effective use of personal qualities and knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of working in a certain field; defined "competence" as an existing and emerging ability to perform a specific activity.

J.E.Usarov in his scientific works defined competence as "experience and knowledge in a certain field or direction, manifestation of readiness to perform activities and the ability of a person to act successfully in various non-standard situations."

According to B. Kh. Khodzhaev, "competence serves to integrate self-development efforts to acquire new personal experience." N. A. Muslimov emphasizes that competence is not the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction.

Methods of diagnosing and correcting the formation of competencies Yu. Asadov, N.Turdiev, S.Akbarova, D.Tumirov, systematized and described in research works. R. Fayzullaev conducted research aimed at solving problems related to the development of information competence in the educational process.

Many scientists and specialists have expressed their opinion on the concepts of competence and competence. For example, in the monographic work "Competence in modern society" by J. Raven: "it consists of a large number of components, many of which are independent of each other ... some components belong more to the cognitive sphere, others to the emotional sphere. These components can complement each other in effective self-management. J. Delor in his lecture "Education - hidden treasure" at the International European Council on Education in the 21st Century explains "the four pillars on which education rests": learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together, learning to live.

These concepts reveal the main content of competence. According to J. Delor, learning to perform means not only having professional skills, but also being competent in a broad sense, that is, being able to work in groups and successfully get out of many difficult situations that arise during work. It should be noted that together with the concept of "competence", there are also cases where the term "skill base" is used as its synonym.

In particular, A.K. In the works of Markova, professional competence in the context of labor psychology was considered as a special subject, while the works related to teacher competence were put forward by L.A. Petrovskaya, N.V. Kuzmin and others.

Although the content of the accepted integrative approaches has been developed, relevant suggestions and recommendations have been given, the definitions given to them are wide and diverse, and at the same time, they all cover certain directions. V. I. Baydenko suggests making some changes in the definition of the concept of competence. This set of components allows a person

to set a goal, achieve success and develop in the specified field of activity. The following conclusions can be drawn from these concepts. Competence is experience and knowledge in a certain field or direction, manifestation of readiness to perform activities, and a person's ability to act successfully in various non-standard situations. This definition given to the concept of competence shows the knowledge and experience acquired by a person in the process of study.

A.A. Verbitsky and O.B. Ermakova believe that the integrative approach is "the main way to improve the quality of general secondary and higher education, and it confidently takes the position of the main methodology in its modernization." These authors emphasized that the following considerations are important for all links of the pedagogical system to successfully involve the educational system:

- changing the structure and content of education: moving from theoretical concepts collected in different educational subjects, separated from each other, to methods that give a universal idea about the environment and implement it through practical and social skills;

- changing the approach to the purpose and results of education: from simple assimilation of the received information by students to social and intellectual culture, to the qualitative formation of the image of the human environment;

- making changes to the structure of the teacher's pedagogical activity: switching from a one-sided presentation of the educational material to conducting a dialogue with students; effective development of student personality:

- introduction of an integrative approach to the environment of higher education; media, social being, family, country, culture, etc. making changes; technological supply reform:

- transition to innovative technologies aimed at the development of student activities; strengthening the organizational, personnel, material-technical and

financial support of the educational system.

The requirement for students to be able to apply the knowledge they have acquired in life in technical higher education institutions is the improvement of DTS and programs, in other words, the integration of the integrative approach into the content of the educational system, the formation and development of the concept of achieving its educational results. The origin of these requirements is the need to update the teaching system in technical higher education institutions, the fact that technical higher education institutions did not satisfy the public, although they can demonstrate the knowledge they have received, but they are not ready to work independently to apply it in their daily and future activities.

According to A.I. Subetto, the integrative approach can be considered as an addition to the existing system of knowledge, skills and competencies. Based on the European experience, it can be noted that the effective use of an integrative approach in the higher education system today provides an opportunity for comprehensive development of the individual. It should be noted that the concept of an integrative approach that appeared in the next decade is natural for the European education system, but it is a novelty for the Uzbekistan education system. The emergence of the term "integrative approach" in turn affected the question of revising the existing category system of pedagogy.

Education based on an integrative approach today is a topic that causes some conflicts, contradictions and different opinions due to its insufficient scientific and methodological research. Currently, there is no stable definition of competence. The concepts of competence and competence are interpreted differently. For example, in the "Encyclopedic Dictionary" authored by B.A. Vvedensky, the following definition is given: "Competence is the range of powers, the range of questions acquired by this person through his knowledge and experience", that is, the knowledge that a person can discuss and has in this or that field of activity.

In education based on an integrative approach, the student becomes the main

participant in the educational process with personal goals and tasks. This approach makes it possible to engage the student in active, conscious activities, develop informational, communicative, educational and cognitive skills, personal potential, form self-esteem, and develop self-management skills.

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